

D6.4

Report on Impact of Game Jams

*Reporting period 01/03/2024
to 29/01/2026*

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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- 1 PU = Public
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CBC	Fonden Creative Business Network
CGJ	Cultural Game Jam
CH	Cultural Hub
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institutions
CI	Creative Industries
CYM	Children, Youth and Media
EPIC-WE	Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments
KEA	KEA European Affairs
LL	Living Lab
NISV	Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision
QH	Quadruple Helix Ecosystem
YC	Youth Citizens

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Executive Summary

Executive Summary

This deliverable, *D6.4 Report on Impact of Cultural Game Jams*, presents the impact assessment of twelve Cultural Game Jams delivered across the Aarhus, Hilversum, and Óbidos Cultural Hubs. It builds on the insights generated in *D4.1 – Report on Game-Making Interventions with Youth in Cultural Heritage Institutions* and *D4.2 – Report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation*, as well as the youth engagement evidence in *D2.3 – Synthesis of EPIC-WE Outcomes*. Together, these sources enable a comprehensive evaluation of how Cultural Game Jams contribute to cultural participation, youth empowerment, creativity, digital skills development and inter-sector collaboration. They also demonstrate how the project's co-creative interventions have generated cultural and social impact within and across the Quadruple Helix (QH) ecosystem, with outcomes interpreted through the WP6 impact indicators to form a coherent, cross-hub impact narrative.

Key objectives of this deliverable are:

- Identification of predicted indicators and KPIs relevant to impact measurement;
- Integration of research results from WP4 and WP2 into a holistic impact assessment;
- Assessment of how impact measurement practices can guide CHIs, CIs and HEIs in adopting and scaling the EPIC-WE ecosystem and model;
- Provision of actionable insights for CHIs, CIs, and HEIs to evaluate and replicate empowered participation models.

In line with these objectives, D6.4 evaluates the transformative, participatory and cultural impacts of EPIC-WE's interventions by synthesising, rather than re-analysing, the empirical findings produced in D2.3, D4.1 and D4.2. These prior deliverables documented the analytical outcomes of CGJs and QH collaborations;

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D6.4 builds upon them to provide a cross-hub synthesis of EPIC-WE's impact. On a wider scale, the objective of WP6 is to enable accurate and meaningful impact measurement while providing valuable tools for ongoing engagement with the project's outputs, including the developed ecosystems, Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jam kits, and capacity-building activities.

To support a clear understanding of how impact emerged across the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, a visual logic model has been developed for each stakeholder group. This model summarises the resources mobilised, activities undertaken, outputs produced, and the resulting outcomes and long-term impacts. The outcomes and impacts in this model correspond to EPIC-WE's seven key impact indicators: *Knowledge & Cultural Understanding, Skill Development, Creativity & Imagination, Playfulness & Fun, Collaboration & Co-creation, Empowered Participation, and Social Connection.*

IMPACT ON YOUTH CITIZENS

Figure 1: Model of EPIC-WE Impact on Youth Citizen stakeholders (YCs)

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Figure 2: Model of EPIC-WE Impact on Higher Education Institution Stakeholders (HEIs)

IMPACT ON CULTURAL HERITAGE INSTITUTIONS

Figure 3: Model of EPIC-WE Impact on Cultural Heritage Institution Stakeholders (CHIs)

IMPACT ON CREATIVE INDUSTRIES

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Figure 4: Model of EPIC-WE Impact on Creative Industry Stakeholder (CI)

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Furthermore, this report adopts [the Europeana Playbook](#) as its narrative and methodological framework, presenting impact as a dynamic, iterative process that unfolds through sensing, recognising, analysing, reflecting and sharing. The Playbook is specifically designed for cultural heritage institutions and creative sector projects, providing tools to map how activities generate social, cultural, and economic impact across multiple stakeholders. Unlike traditional linear logic models, the Playbook emphasises participatory, stakeholder-specific pathways, capturing both qualitative and quantitative transformations, and supporting iterative reflection and co-creation. Its structured yet flexible approach makes it particularly suitable for EPIC-WE, where Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) operate as co-creative laboratories across diverse contexts. Insights from a speed-networking exercise and a Mentimeter survey during an EPIC-WE consortium meeting in Óbidos (February 2024) were analysed to identify shared themes and values, which informed the selection of indicators. Using these WP6 key indicators – *Knowledge & Cultural Understanding, Skill development, Creativity and Imagination, Playful Learning and Engagement, Collaboration and Co-creation, Empowered Participation, and Social Connections* – the report outlines how GCJs fostered transformative learning, cross-sector collaboration, and youth empowerment.

The findings presented in this report serve as a benchmark for the forthcoming public impact measurement guide (D6.5 - Publication on Impact) which will be published on the EPIC-WE Project website. The aim of this publication is to guide HEIs, CIs and CHIs in conducting relevant and correct impact tracking aligned with the EPIC-WE overall framework. On a wider scale, the objective of WP6 is to enable accurate and meaningful impact measurement while providing valuable tools for ongoing engagement with the project's outputs, including ecosystems, Cultural Hub model, Cultural Game Jam kits, and capacity-building activities. WP6 also aims to deliver targeted capacity-building and policy recommendations for Creative Industries (CIs), Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). A key

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focus of this work package is fostering strong connections with stakeholders and policymakers by integrating them into a collaborative, three-step process for policy development.

Task 6.1, led by the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV) and in collaboration with Fonden Creative Business Cup (CBC) and KEA European Affairs (KEA), centres on impact measurement through a comprehensive needs analysis. A primary step of this analysis involved creating a change pathway to map expected impacts and defining key indicators to be measured.

How to read this report

This report is structured into five main chapters.

Chapter 1 introduces the EPIC-WE project and sets out the role of D6.4 within WP6, outlining how impact is understood and why Cultural Game Jams serve as key sites of cultural and participatory innovation.

Chapter 2 provides the core impact narrative, offering a qualitative, story-driven account of how change unfolded across the three Cultural Hubs, drawing on evidence from D2.3, D4.1, and D4.2, as well as the conceptual foundations from D3.2 and D3.3, and testimonials given by all relevant stakeholders within the project.

Chapter 3 presents the evaluation, mapping outcomes against the seven WP6 impact indicators and visualising the effects across the Quadruple Helix stakeholder groups.

Chapter 4 presents the methodology, explaining the impact measurement approach developed in Task 6.1, the use of the Europeana Playbook, and the indicators guiding the analysis.

Chapter 5 concludes the report and discusses how this impact narrative contributes to the development of the public impact measurement guide (D6.5) and the broader sustainability of the EPIC-WE framework.

Disclaimer: The report has been produced with various sources of and project documentation. As these materials include personal information about the participants, the names and personal information have been anonymized. The quotes provided in the report only state the source (i.e. researcher, game jam participant etc.) with the name and place of the CGJ.

Introduction

01

1. Introduction

EPIC-WE (*Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments*) is a Horizon Europe-funded project (2023-2026) that explores how game-making can serve as a powerful tool for culture-making. It aims to empower young citizens to explore European Values and actively participate in shaping European culture and their own futures by ‘imagining, creating and exchanging cultural values and heritage through game-making’. The project introduces new models for cultural innovation, collaboration, and empowered participation in game-making culture through its Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and Cultural Hub model that brings together Youth Citizens (YCs), Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), Creative Industries (CIs) and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) as equal partners in cultural production and innovation.

To operationalise this ecosystem and model, EPIC-WE developed and tested Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) across three European Cultural Hubs – Aarhus (Denmark), Hilversum (The Netherlands) and Óbidos (Portugal). These Cultural Hubs act as living laboratories, where partners experiment with new ways of learning, collaborating and generating cultural values through co-creative practices. To achieve this, 12 interventions have taken place – in the form of Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) – across these three European sites. The backbone of this project is the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem (EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem), a transferable framework enabling diverse actors and stakeholders to collaborate on equal terms and to generate new cultural forms, narratives and policies for cultural innovation.

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Figure 5: EPIC-WE core concepts

The Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV) leads Task 6.1 in researching and defining impact measurement methodologies for the EPIC-WE project. This task focuses on identifying key performance indicators (KPIs) and relevant data points to assess the effectiveness of the CGJs carried out in Work Package 4 (WP4). Building on the conceptual foundations of [D2.3 Synthesis of EPIC-WE outcomes](#), [D3.2 Protocol 1](#), [D3.2 Protocol 2](#), [D3.3 Report on the design and construction of ecosystems and game jams](#), [D4.1 Game-Making Interventions](#) and [D4.2 Quadruple Helix Operationalisation](#), this report defines impact in qualitative and relational terms. Rather than quantifying the impact, it focuses on the impactfulness: the lived transformations experienced by Youth Citizens (YCs), partners, and institutions as they co-created cultural value through games, dialogue, and collective reflection.

The EPIC-WE project was a model of glocal co-creation: across hubs, the project demonstrated how Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), Creative Industries (CIs), Higher Education (HEs) and Youth Citizens (TCs) can create living laboratories together for participatory cultural innovation (Janssen, M., 2025, Quadruple Helix Operationalisation). EPIC-WE was, in fact, conceived as a Design-Based Research and Innovation (DBR) project in which practice and research mutually inform each

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other (Janssen, M., 2025, Quadruple Helix Operationalisation). The CGJs function as an iterative experiment through which new approaches for joint and co-creative work were tested and refined. Each CGJ embodies the six principles of democratisation, equal and transformative partnerships, meeting in the middle, co-creation for public good, real-world engagement, and empowered participation. These six principles can be fully read in [the report on Quadruple Helix Operationalisation](#).

The structure of this report follows the objectives outlined in Task 6.1, covering:

- The identification of predicted **indicators and KPIs** relevant to impact measurement while the interventions were running (WP4). The analyses from WP4 function as a benchmark for the impact measurement.
- Supporting the preparation of a publicly available guide on impact measurement (D6.5)
- The role of impact measurement in guiding the adoption of the **EPIC-WE framework**.

In line with these objectives, D6.4 evaluates the transformative, participatory and cultural impacts of EPIC-WE's interventions by synthesising, rather than re-analysing, the empirical findings produced in D4.1 (Game-Making Framework), D4.2 (Quadruple Helix Operationalisation) and D2.3 (Synthesis of EPIC-WE Outcomes). These prior deliverables documented the research results of the CGJs and QH collaborations. D6.4 builds upon them to provide a cross-hub synthesis of impact. By establishing a strong foundation for impact assessment, this analysis contributes to the long-term sustainability of the project, ensuring that CGJs, Cultural Hubs, and other EPIC-WE initiatives can be evaluated, refined, and adapted for broader application in the cultural sector and beyond.

Impact Narrative

**Cultural Game Jams:
A Story of Change,
Creativity and
Empowered
Participation**

02

2. Impact Narrative – Cultural Game Jams: A Story of Change, Creativity and Empowered Participation

This chapter assesses the impact of the CGJs across the three EPIC-WE Cultural Hubs, using qualitative evidence drawn from D4.1, D4.2 and D2.3 to assess the impact of the EPIC-WE project.

Impact within EPIC-WE is defined as the extent to which co-creative participation transforms attitudes, relationships, capacities and practices across the QH Ecosystem. Following the Europeana Playbook approach, this chapter provides a story-driven, qualitative narrative arc that shows how impact unfolded across the EPIC-WE CGJs by synthesising findings presented in D2.3, D4.1 and D4.2, interpreting them through the 7 earlier established Impact Indicators.

2.1 Setting the Scene: Cultural Game Jams as Events of Transformation

The digital age is reshaping how young people engage with cultural heritage, creativity, and innovation. Across Europe, CHIs and policymakers are striving to foster digital innovation and inclusivity in the creative industries. However, a critical question remains: how can youth – who are often excluded from decision-making processes – meaningfully participate in shaping the future of cultural innovation?

The EPIC-WE project seeks to address this challenge by fostering a QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem with Cultural Hubs that brings together youth, institutions, policymakers, and industry to co-create new interactive cultural experiences at the intersection of cultural heritage, storytelling and play (Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K.,

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2024, [D3.2: Protocol 1](#)). At the heart of this initiative are a series of Cultural Game Jams: dynamic game-making events that are similar to hackathons, built around a central theme and structured for collaborative co-creation and cultural-creative learning. Game jams are widely acclaimed for game design education and shared entry points for future game developers, fostering experiential and constructivist learning and learning-by-doing attitudes, making them an engaging social site for learning. (Kultima et al., 2023; Costa et al., 2024).

The CGJs organised within the EPIC-WE project brought together young creators across various disciplines for a short but intensive period of time to design and develop games in a group effort. Through participation, experimentation and innovation, they created games that challenged the conventional narratives of their cultural or societal futures whilst strengthening European cultural heritage and values such as democracy, human rights, gender equality, and the richness of cultural concerns. In doing so, the CGJs aimed to:

- **Explore** and develop new models for cultural collaboration and empowered participation.
- **Create** and exchange cultural values and heritage through game-making practices.
- **Establish** Cultural Hubs across Europe to support these initiatives.

The project's ambitions extend well beyond game creation. As established in D3.2, CGJs are dynamic, time-bound interventions where young people collaborate with institutions and creative partners to explore culture through four CGJ phases: Experience, Play, Imagine and Create (Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K., 2024, [D3.2: Protocol 2](#)). This way, the YCs were invited to explore European cultural heritage in inclusive participatory ways, and to reimagine how cultural sites, artifacts, meaning, and values can be lived and expressed together with cultural heritage institutions,

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higher education institutions and creative partners. Through these events, EPIC-WE's Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and Cultural Hub model enabled YCs, CHIs, CIs and HEIs to jointly explore how cultural innovation can be socially inclusive and future-oriented (Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K., 2024, D3.2: Protocol 2). The CGJs therefore extend beyond game creation: they operate as frameworks for empowered participation, aligning with D3.3 Principles 1, 2 and 3, which define collaboration as equal partnership grounded in mutual learning and meeting each other in the middle, rather than hierarchical coordination (Janssen, M., 2025, D4.2: Quadruple Helix Operationalisation; Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R. T., 2025, [D3.3: Report on Insights from the Design and Construction of Ecosystems and Game Jams](#)).

Empowered participation is one of EPIC-WE's central missions. Through hands-on game-making activities, EPIC-WE aims to equip young people with the cultural-creative imagination and skills needed to address cultural themes and societal challenges with curiosity, creativity, agency and imagination. Rather than being positioned as passive recipients of cultural heritage, they are invited to actively participate in its evolution, ensuring their voices help define what cultural heritage means today and in the future. By actively engaging them in the process of cultural co-creation and innovation, they are not just learning to make games – they are learning to shape narratives, challenge existing frameworks, and claim their role as co-creators of European culture. By claiming their roles as co-creators, they contribute to a more inclusive and innovative European cultural landscape.

Throughout the project, we have looked to existing work, good practices and lessons learned to guide how we assess the extent to which all stakeholders and especially the youth citizens were empowered participants. As we continue to explore the impact of our CGJs, it is important to critically examine whose voices are represented, how power dynamics shape participation, and whether the methods and frameworks used to organise the CGJs reinforce or challenge existing inequalities: How do existing

power structures shape participation in CGJs? Who is included in this process and who remains on the margins? Because participatory processes are not inherently equitable: power must be actively redistributed to ensure that marginalised groups are not just present at the event, but can also meaningfully engage in shaping the conversations (Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R. T., 2025, D3.3. Report on Insights from the Design and Construction of Ecosystems and Game Jams). EPIC-WE's impact narrative therefore examines whose voices are represented, how power circulates among stakeholders, and how youth are invited and supported to act as co-creators and co-owners, rather than end users or beneficiaries.

2.1.1 The Places Where Our Story Takes Place

The CGJs were organised across three Cultural Hubs in different European countries where young creatives from HEIs and high schools were encouraged to engage with CHIs and CIs to produce games that blend cultural heritage storytelling, creativity, and play.

In Aarhus, Denmark, the CGJs unfold at the intersection of academia, art and industry, where young participants engage with the artworks and installations at the Aros Art Museum. In this Cultural Hub, the focus was on using value-sensitive design, cultural heritage sensitivity and societal belonging, to foster cultural collaboration and empowered participation.

In Hilversum, the Netherlands, the CGJs encouraged young people to critically engage with media history and rethink the role of cultural memory in the digital age. The Cultural Hub takes on a deeply reflective tone, inviting participants to engage with thematic issues linked to current societal problems and contemporary

challenges. Recognising the diverse needs within the 16-24 age group, it also adopted an inclusive strategy, promoting multi-generational collaboration.

In Óbidos, Portugal, the CGJs were deeply embedded in the town's historic landscape, where medieval heritage meets contemporary storytelling. The hub specialised in Children, Youth and Media (CYM) creation, emphasising self-expression and participation, whilst addressing European Union values of equality and democracy to promote plural voices, to foster diverse and inclusive participation, and to contribute to a rich cultural heritage landscape.

Each Cultural Hub operated as a living laboratory, where cultural collaboration unfolds within and through existing (global, glocal, local) cultural heritage ecosystems (Janssen, M., 2025, Quadruple Helix Operationalisation). Rather than constructing external innovation spaces, the cultural heritage sites transformed their own cultural environments into participatory spaces of co-design and experimentation. Together, they formed a pan-European network for youth-driven cultural innovation in game-making and collective cultural transformation.

2.1.2 The Voices that Shape Our Story

There are several important stakeholders that are the voices that shape our EPIC-WE story. At the centre of the narrative are the Youth Citizens (YCs), young creatives from the ages of 16 to 24 who engage with cultural heritage through reflective and engaged play, design and storytelling. They bring fresh cultural perspectives and curiosity to the process, embodying the project's ambition to empower youth as co-creators of European culture. For many, this is an opportunity to gain new cultural-creative skills, expand their cultural-creative horizons, and engage in a space where their voices and ideas matter.

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Surrounding these YCs are the institutions that co-shape the QH Ecosystem:

- **HEIs** play a crucial role, with researchers, educators, and experts from diverse fields – ranging from game design, education, to culture and media studies – working to integrate youth perspectives into research and innovation. Through EPIC-WE, these institutions explore new ways of engaging students, bridging academia and real-world cultural practices.
- And then we have **CHIs** – museums, libraries, digital media archives, heritage sites, and art galleries – who stand at a crossroads between history and transformation of the future. By collaborating with HEIs, CIs and YCs, they seek to move beyond static exhibits, finding interactive and playful ways to connect with new generations.
- Lastly, there are also the **CIs** – a diverse network of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), start-ups, freelancers, and cultural entrepreneurs. For them, the CGJs provide a platform for experimentation, co-creation, and potential business opportunities, fostering a dynamic exchange between industry professionals, students, HEIs, and CHIs.

Throughout this report, we will show first-hand accounts of these four stakeholders, illustrating the real-world impact of EPIC-WE through lived experiences. Collaboration between these stakeholders embodied D3.3 principles 2 and 3 (“Equal and Transformative Partnerships” and “Meeting in the Middle”). Rather than hierarchical coordination, hubs developed negotiated reciprocity: each helix in the QH Ecosystem contributed domain expertise and input while collaborating and co-creating with other partners, sectors or disciplines. (Janssen, M., 2025, Quadruple Helix Operationalisation; Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R. T., 2025, D3.3: Report on Insights from the Design and Construction of Ecosystems and Game Jams).

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The following tables present the completed Change Pathways for each stakeholder group in the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix: Youth Citizens (YC), Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI), Higher Education Institutions (HEI) and Creative Industries (CI). These pathways synthesise the aimed results and illustrate how project resources and activities translate into outputs, outcomes and long-term impacts. They follow the Europeana Impact Playbook structure and align with the Specific Outcomes defined at the start of the EPIC-WE project.

CHANGE PATHWAY FOR YOUTH CITIZENS

Europeana Playbook Element	Description
Resources	Cultural Hub infrastructure; CGJ facilitators and mentors; CHI-provided heritage materials; CGJ Kit; digital and game development tools; youth recruitment networks.
Activities	Cultural Game Jams (local & glocal); heritage workshops; team-based design & prototyping; cross-cultural exchange; mentoring by CHI/CI/HEI partners.
Outputs	12 CGJs delivered; CGJ formats adapted to age groups & heritage themes; 108 youth-created game prototypes; reflection materials; 8 further developed games with culture from the cultural game prototypes created by the young CGJ teams.
Short-term Outcomes (Immediate Results)	Increased knowledge of heritage & European values; improved cultural, creative, digital & collaborative skills; enhanced sense of cultural belonging, wellbeing & empowerment; new cross-cultural friendships;

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	confidence to express cultural-creative ideas; the opportunity to connect with industry experts which leads to youth building up their professional network.
Long-term Outcomes (Medium-term Changes)	Youth pursue creative/digital/cultural interests; special attention paid to inclusion of female & non-binary youth for increased confidence in the game/tech domains, to stimulate youth from more diverse gender backgrounds to engage game-making as culture-making and enter the game sector; sustained engagement with CHIs/CIs; youth influence local cultural narratives.
Impact (Long-term Change)	Youth voices integrated into cultural institutions & policy; emergence of youth-led game studios (≥4 companies, 20 jobs); greater gender & diversity representation in CIs; youth recognised as cultural co-creators in Europe.

Table 1: Change Pathway for YCs established in the design phase of the project

CHANGE PATHWAY FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE INSTITUTIONS (CHIs)

Europeana	Description
Playbook Element	
Resources	CHI staff (educators, curators, organisational staff); cultural heritage sites, collections, and archives; mediation & educational expertise; Cultural Hub spaces; outreach networks

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Activities	Supplying heritage themes and curated content; co-facilitating CGJs; mentoring youth; participating in Cultural Hubs; supporting game selection & further development of games through and for culture
Outputs	New youth-centred practice models; heritage-based prototypes; documentation of CHI–CI–HEI collaboration; use cases of cultural innovation through games
Short-term Outcomes (Immediate Results)	CHIs gain new methods for youth engagement; improved confidence in working with CIs/HEIs; recognition of games as cultural mediators and vice versa; new partnerships formed locally
Long-term Outcomes (Medium-term Changes)	CHIs adopt more participatory- and innovation-oriented mindsets; institutionalised co-creation practices; youth perspectives integrated into exhibitions and programming
Impact (Long-term Change)	Replication of CGJs by ≥60 CHIs across Europe; strengthened position of CHIs in cultural-creative value chains; increased cultural democracy and youth inclusion in heritage sectors

Table 2: Change Pathway for CHIs established in the design phase of the project

CHANGE PATHWAY FOR HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (HEIs)

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Europeana Playbook Element	Description
Resources	Academic staff; DBR expertise; teaching infrastructure; study programmes and student involvement; game & design research capacities
Activities	Research design for CGJs; design, mentoring and facilitation of CGJs; data collection; integration of CGJ outputs into teaching and study programmes; participation in Cultural Hubs and glocal exchanges
Outputs	New teaching approaches and methods (CGJs, game-based learning, participatory design, game-making as culture-making); research papers; white papers; conceptual frameworks; student involvement in applied research and innovation
Short-term Outcomes (Immediate Results)	Interdisciplinary collaboration increases; HEIs gain tested hands-on methods for youth engagement; new applied research emerges; CGJ as teaching and learning method; enhanced HEI–CHI–CI coordination
Long-term Outcomes (Medium-term Changes)	Integration of game-making and co-creation approaches into HEI curricula and study programmes; HEIs become regional innovation actors; long-term partnerships with CHIs & CIs
Impact (Long-term Change)	≥8 new R&I projects initiated based on Cultural Hub and CGJ insights; HEIs improve societal relevance of teaching and research; stronger bridges between academia and cultural/creative sectors

Table 3: Change Pathway for HEIs established in the design phase of the project

CHANGE PATHWAY FOR CREATIVE INDUSTRIES (CIs)

Europeana Playbook Element	Description
Resources	Game experts and mentors; industry knowledge; production tools; professional networks; prototyping and game development expertise
Activities	Mentoring youth teams; co-developing prototypes; contributing to Cultural Hubs; evaluating and refining game concepts; showcasing games at industry events
Outputs	8 refined games with culture; industry showcases; documented collaboration models; strengthened CHI–CI–HEI knowledge exchange; engaging the future workforce
Short-term Outcomes (Immediate Results)	CIs gain insight into culture- and value-driven game-making; exposure to youth creativity; new cross-sector partnerships; inspiration for heritage-based game-making and products
Long-term Outcomes (Medium-term Changes)	Growth in collaborations with CHIs/HEIs; integration of cultural heritage themes in CI production workflows; adoption of responsible and inclusive design approaches
Impact (Long-term Change)	≥20 CIs new to QH partnerships or Cultural Hubs; expansion of the culture- and value-driven games market; strengthened socioeconomic contribution of the European games sector; more diverse creative workforce

Table 4: Change Pathway for CIs established in the design phase of the project

2.1.3 A typical Cultural Game Jam

In recent years, game jams have emerged as a novel method and approach for introducing youth to diverse educational, cultural, and societal topics (Fowler et al., 2016; Lai et al., 2021; Costa et al., 2024) while serving as platforms for research and innovation (Kultima and Laiti, 2019). Game jams are social, collaborative events where participants come together to ideate, develop, and prototype games within a limited time frame (Kultima, 2015). The goal is to foster creativity and rapid game (concept) development (Meriläinen et al., 2020). These events vary in duration, typically spanning from a few hours to a weekend, encouraging focused development without excessive planning. Participants come from different backgrounds and thus integrate experiences and competencies across disciplines, e.g., design, technology, programming, or visual arts, providing relevance in the enculturation of aspiring game developers who might look towards entering the industry (Holflod K., Nørgård, R.T, Eriksson E., 2024, p.2).

Photo 1: CGJ in Aarhus, Denmark

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Photo 2: CGJ in Hilversum, the Netherlands

Photo 3: CGJ in Óbidos, Portugal

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EPIC-WE’s CGJs aimed to empower young people with social and cultural game-making skills through development of games through and for culture in CGJs. These CGJs were the initial results of applying the QH Cultural Hub model to create games with cultural significance (Almeida W., Luz F., Fernandes P., Fonseca M., 2024, p.3). The project’s CGJ process developed a progression and taxonomical model that scaffolds the CGJ process for facilitators and participants with its Experience, Play, Imagine and Create (E-P-I-C) phases (Eriksson, E., Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R.T., 2024).

Figure 6: EPIC-WE CGJ Process

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These four phases combine divergent and convergent thinking within an ideating and design domain. *Experience* targets culture and cultural heritage exploration through participants' divergent ideation and brainstorming within the four CGJ categories, while *Play* aims to focus this exploration into emerging cultural (heritage) concepts through participants' convergent ideation to integrate elements from the four CGJ categories into an idea for a game through/for culture. Similarly, *Imagine* targets envisioning cultural game worlds and game-making through participants' divergent design and game mock-ups, while *Create* transforms design ideas and game mock-ups through participants' convergence on a single game through/for culture concept and playable prototype to be showcased at the concluding CGJ Expo (Eriksson, E., Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R. T., 2024).

Each Cultural Hub in Aarhus, Hilversum and Óbidos hosted four Cultural Game Jams (12 in total), in which they brought together a unique combination of participants, themes, and cultural heritage sites and collections. The structure of these Cultural Game Jams varied, ranging from intense two-day events to extended sessions spanning several months. A typical Cultural Game Jam unfolded in four distinct moments:

- **Kick-off & Team Formation:** The young participants meet, form teams, and explore their cultural-creative journey ahead.
- **Inspiration & Ideation:** Visits to cultural heritage collections, archives, or sites are incorporated to spark ideas, followed by brainstorming sessions and cultural heritage concept development.
- **Prototyping & Playtesting:** Teams start crafting their cultural game prototypes, iterating their stories based on expert feedback and peer testing to investigate which elements of their games still need improvement.

- **Presentation & Reflection:** The event ends with final presentations, in which each team showcases their finished cultural game prototypes to their fellow game jammers and a wider audience.

The distinct moments of a Cultural Game Jam created a structured yet flexible cultural environment for creativity to flourish. However, each event also revealed key insights into participation, empowerment, and engagement with cultural heritage, which will be discussed in the following sections.

2.2 The Journey

The journey of EPIC-WE's CGJs is one of creativity, collaboration and discovery. This section delves into the lived experiences of the people involved, highlighting key moments that shaped the Cultural Game Jam process. Through a close examination of how the CGJs unfolded – their structure, participant dynamics and specific outcomes – we begin to see how empowered participation of young minds takes shape in practice. This chapter offers a look at how YCs, HEIs, CHIs and CIs learned from one another and transformed ideas into playable, cultural experiences. By drawing from testimonials, we uncover how these experiences shaped the participants' sense of empowerment, their social experiences and their engagement with cultural heritage. In the context of this report, *testimonials* refer to qualitative first-person accounts collected throughout the project, including short statements, [expert interviews](#) and reflective accounts from youth participants, Youth Advisory Board members, facilitators, cultural professionals, creative industry mentors and academic partners, that document their experiences, perceptions and learning processes. Rather than isolating testimonials in a standalone subsection, they appear throughout the analysis to deepen and contextualise findings. The overall

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assessment draws on the 7 core indicators, KPI's established in T6.1 and aligned with the aims of EPIC-WE and the Europeana Impact Playbook method. This list of Impact Indicators serve as benchmarks and can be seen as *conceptual lenses* rather than data categories. They help to understand *how* the CGJs produced cultural and social impact across events, hubs, and partners:

Impact Topic	Explanation
Knowledge & Cultural Understanding	Development of new cultural knowledge, insights, and awareness; deepened understanding of cultural heritage through expression and interpretation, sensory encounters, and creative translation across all QH stakeholders.
Skills	Acquisition or strengthening of cultural, creative, technical, collaborative, reflective, and idea-generating skills; cross-sector skill exchange enabled by Quadruple Helix collaboration.
Creativity & Imagination	Ability to generate novel ideas, reimagine cultural narratives, and use cultural heritage as game-making material in game concepts, prototypes, and storytelling.
Playfulness & Fun	Engagement, motivation, and learning fostered through cultural and playful methods; using cultural creativity to stimulate curiosity, experimentation, and heritage reinterpretation.
Collaboration & Co-Creation	Quality of teamwork, negotiation, and shared creativity; emergence of new relationships, togetherness, cross-sector interactions, and collective decision-making within the QH ecosystem.
Empowered Participation	Experiences of agency, voice, influence, co-ownership and co-authorship among all stakeholder groups; ability to shape decisions, processes, and cultural meaning-making within the Cultural Hubs.
Social Connections	Formation and strengthening of interpersonal bonds, sense of belonging, trust, and community; continuity of relationships beyond the events and across QH partners.

Table 5: Impact Assessment Indicators

2.2.1 The Promise: Cultural Game Jams as Catalyst for Cultural and Social Change

The CGJs were envisioned as immersive, collaborative cultural heritage interventions that would allow young people to engage deeply with heritage, values and experiment with new forms of cultural expression. These Cultural Game Jams serve both as an educational and an innovative event, fostering skills, agency, empowered participation and new cultural narratives. The intended ambitions were as follows:

- Explore the potential of games and game-making practices to empower the youth and contribute to strengthening of European values and cultural participation.
- Transform HEIs, CHIs, and CIs into Cultural Hubs for co-creation, where young people, researchers, and cultural actors collaborate on meaningful, innovative projects and co-create as equal partners.
- Empower youth with new skills in cultural game design, storytelling, and collaboration, and position them not just as participants, but as co-creators and culture-makers, designing interactive cultural experiences that challenge dominant narratives, experiment with new ideas, and contribute to a sustainable model for cultural engagement beyond traditional museum, gallery or heritage settings.
- Strengthen cultural and educational capacities for youth-centred innovation.

The intended impact, therefore, was multi-layered: to foster cultural-creative learning, inspire cultural creativity through game-making, strengthen cross-sector and interdisciplinary collaboration, develop agency and contribute to a renewed, youth-driven understanding of cultural heritage.

2.2.2 The Reality: Successes and Frictions

Overall, the CGJs delivered meaningful learning and positive experiences for the various stakeholders. Yet, not all aspects unfolded as intended: the impact of the events was shaped by varying levels of preparation, differing group dynamics, and particularities of each hub.

Knowledge & cultural understanding

Knowledge development is not just about understanding the skills involved in game making. One of our ambitions was to foster a deep understanding of cultural heritage, cultural themes, storytelling and game-making tools for cultural-creative expression and social engagement, as a benefit for our European society.

“Unfortunately, I believe games are not taken as seriously as other types of art, like traditional art or film, which is a great shame because a lot of people who do engage with games, beyond their entertainment value they can have a deep cultural and personal impact. I hope that by creating projects like this, it helps build a bridge between games and more traditional art.”

- Creative Industry stakeholder, Aarhus (CI)

Participants engaged with artworks, archives, local histories, cities, landscapes and civic narratives, not as passive visitors, but as cultural co-creators. This reflects D3.2's principles 3, 6 and 7, which frame game-making as a process of curiosity-driven cultural reinterpretation, and the creation of new cultural expressions (Nørgård &

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Holfod, 2025, [D3.2 Protocols 2](#), pp. 37–39). This also resonates with D2.3, where games are understood as cultural spaces in which young people actively work with heritage, values and societal themes. Rather than simply attaching a cultural topic to a game idea, the most meaningful forms of participation emerged when games served as both artefacts of engagement and connection, as well as specific cultural worlds that function as spaces for and processes of cultural meaning-making, identity negotiation, and societal reflection. In this sense, game-making became a way for participants to explore cultural identity, negotiate heritage viewpoints and engage critically with cultural material, demonstrating how playful creation can support deeper cultural participation and civic reflection.

"It's a nice experience for young people to participate because it helps them enrich themselves and [make] more creative games and know more about their roots. It's a cultural way of teaching children about culture and their countries."

- Game Jam participant, Óbidos (YC)

"If I had to describe the Game Jam, I'd say it was an educational and fun experience. I learned a lot. I tried something I haven't done before, which is also really fun."

- Game Jam participant, Aarhus (YC)

In practice, knowledge deepened most strongly when cultural encounters were sensory, embedded, embodied and guided, via for instance workshops, artwalks, depot tours, street walks and sensory exercises. Guided tours, visual prompts, artistic interventions, archival materials and various more types of sensory encounters helped to transform cultural heritage into an active game-making material, where it might usually be perceived as something abstract or distant. Such cultural heritage

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environments enabled youth to form deeper connections to heritage, translating cultural materials into game mechanics, interactions, narratives and stories.

"It seems like the participants are actively engaged in the reflective process and are demonstrating competencies in collaboration, understanding of project goals, and productive communication. The art-walks provide a platform or perhaps framework for reflection, enabling an environment or a space where ideas are shared and connections are made."

- Researcher, Observational Grid, Aarhus (HEI)

For many participants, the CGJs were their first hands-on experience with game-making. For some participants, the event marked their first meaningful engagement with cultural and artistic themes in a creative setting:

"A couple of the participants from coding/programming backgrounds expressed that they didn't normally engage with culture and art. But, they were becoming more interested in jamming at ARoS and thinking about cultural and artistic potentials in game-making and game design."

- Researcher, Observational Grid, Aarhus (HEI)

This testimonial highlights the potential of CGJs to encourage the young participants to see culture and heritage as sources of creative inspiration in their storytelling process. This immersion into a real-world creative process provided an opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in a practical setting.

"A key benefit of including game jams and games into our cultural programme is that young people create a relation with the cultural heritage. Now I see digital

games in another way, I see them as more educational games, not just for entertainment."

- Óbidos Municipality (CHI)

Moreover, participants with backgrounds in disciplines such as computer science, design studies, visual arts, or those with passion for games had the opportunity to gain new insights into how games can be conceptualised and developed – whether digitally or as a paper prototype.

Overall, participants became increasingly curious as the activities unfolded. Across the three participating Cultural Hubs, the CGJs demonstrated a positive and diverse impact on the participants' cultural knowledge, awareness of cultural heritage and understanding of creative production processes. For many YCs, the CGJs opened a pathway to engage with culture in a new, accessible and playful way.

"It was funny and different to understand how each person looks at something that is supposedly the same as others, but they feel different things, very different even, things that we probably wouldn't even think about, and they come to something that frees them and makes them more comfortable. That gave us some inspiration to take a mere castle, kings, queens, normal things, and think a bit outside the normal, in a way that we bring together things we are more comfortable with, things we like, and return to being more common, so to speak."

- Game Jam participant, Óbidos (YC)

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This testimonial highlights how CGJs empower participants to reinterpret history, and to not see cultural heritage as a fixed narrative, but as a dynamic, personal, and playful experience. Rather than simply replicating historical themes, participants used their understanding and interpretations of cultural heritage as a starting point for imaginative reinterpretation, embedding their own identities, interests, and emotions into their cultural game concepts.

While during some CGJs a slightly deeper cultural integration was achieved compared to other iterations, these variations often reflected contextual differences. Most importantly though, the CGJs showed that cultural knowledge grows when engagement and interpretation is participatory and when cultural heritage is activated as material for creation rather than only didactic instruction. Through this approach, participants left the CGJs with not only expanded knowledge but also a sense of ownership and insight into cultural meaning-making.

Skills development

EPIC-WE wanted to equip young participants with practical and transferable skills that extend beyond game-making, by providing them with an immersive learning experience where creativity, (technical) game developing skills and collaboration come together with cultural heritage and values in an engaging environment. The CGJs acted as living laboratories where youth citizens – together with CHIs, CIs and HEIs – could develop these diverse skills. D2.3 characterises the CGJs as *cultural laboratories*, which aligns directly with WP6’s interpretation of impact as iterative, relational, and experience-based. The data from the twelve CGJs demonstrates that cultural game-making is not just a site of creativity but a process of cultural negotiation where youth, CHIs, CIs, and HEIs co-create new understandings, identities, and cultural futures. Participants of the CGJs practiced cultural heritage

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ideation, prototyping, coding, reimagination, narrative building, playtesting, and games through/for culture creation. Yet beyond learning how to improve and develop these skills, the CGJs also cultivated a space to develop communication, negotiation, and time management – skills essential to collaborative cultural work.

Many participants reported gaining a deeper understanding of game design principles, cultural storytelling, and teamwork dynamics. For some, this was their first exposure to such a cultural-creative process, helping them build confidence in their ability to contribute meaningfully to the creative game development through engaging cultural heritage and learning by doing and working together.

"Cultural Game Jams add value to the domain of games, because it's a good challenge that helps us build soft skills and help us exercise our creativity for future games."

- Game Jam participant, Óbidos (YC)

"The most significant for me was just finding that everyone has their own background with different skills and abilities they could apply to the game, and everyone is trying to jam it into one creative project in a short amount of time. It was quite surprising how chaotic it actually came to be. But we eventually started finding a line. We could still follow through. Changing plans in the middle of the night is completely fine."

- Game Jam participant, Hilversum (YC)

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Participants strengthened idea-generating and problem-solving skills, as they were required to think on their feet, iterate rapidly, and adapt their ideas based on feedback and limited time. The process of translating abstract cultural heritage ideas into playable game prototypes helped to enhance both critical thinking, cultural imagination, and creative execution. This exposure to game-making tools and frameworks broadened their understanding of the field of game-making.

“It was quite strong to experience how some of the groups that struggled most with game-making and game design overcame those challenges and experienced quite a transformation of both technical/creative capabilities and cultural/gameful imagination.”

- Facilitator Post-GJ Reflection on Practical Execution, Aarhus (CHI)

“And the other thing I'd say is how much we can actually push ourselves. Like, working throughout the night. We actually had the schedule to do rapid prototyping from 10pm till 8am. So, we were supposed to be working throughout the night. And some of us did that. And I think it showed how much we can push ourselves when we have the right direction.”

- Game Jam participant, Hilversum (YC)

Additionally, the multidisciplinary nature of the game jams encouraged participants to develop communication and co-creation skills and, as they had to articulate their ideas, negotiate within their teams, and present their concepts to game experts, as well as a wider audience. These skills extend beyond game design and are

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transferable to many other areas, including education, professional collaboration, and creative problem-solving.

“Communication is one of the skills I improved during the Game Jam. Cause that was a really big thing about the whole process. We were in groups with people I had never met before. And we had some miscom... actually, I wouldn't call it miscommunication, but we had times that if we'd had communicated differently, I would have done things differently. I really learned from that.”

- Game Jam participant, Aarhus (YC)

It's worth pointing out that core principle 1 in D3.2 showed that even with different CGJ formats (fixed, flexible, or freeform), facilitators managed to scaffold skills according to the needs of their participants without constraining local imagination, despite using three different approaches.

Moreover, skill development that unfolded through the QH mechanisms described in D3.3 Principle 2 (equal and transformative partnerships) created conditions for cross-sector skill exchange: curators and educators shared cultural insights, designers shared prototyping strategies, researchers integrated reflective tools, and youth citizens contributed fresh perspectives on European cultural heritage. Principle 3 in D3.3 (“meeting in the middle”) required all stakeholders to negotiate terms, methods, and vocabularies, which fostered adaptability and skills around collaboration.

Most importantly, skill acquisition was highly relational: participants learned by doing, observing, being challenged and by receiving feedback from peers, experts, and facilitators. These dynamics reflect the Europeana Playbook's emphasis on active

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participation and co-creation as key drivers of impact. Across Cultural Hubs, participants discovered new competencies as they moved from uncertainty to ownership. The CGJs, therefore, acted as transformative cultural spaces where cultural-creative skills emerged not from instruction but from participation within a shared CGJ process.

Creativity & imagination

One of the main aims of our Cultural Game Jam format was to encourage participants to push their creative boundaries and think in unconventional ways with cultural heritage. The Cultural Game Jams provided a vibrant environment for imagination and idea-generation that encouraged participants to explore and experiment freely. Across Cultural Hubs and CGJs, participants used cultural heritage both as a starting point for imaginative exploration - and as game-making material – remixing artwork, reframing civic issues, and translating myths and histories into cultural narratives and game worlds. This directly reflects D3.2's principles 3 and 6, which position curiosity-driven cultural exploration and interpretative innovation as fundamental mechanisms of cultural game-making.

“I think the biggest outcome of the CGJs is the chance for youth to engage in a creative experience that shows the value of their imagination and world making. Especially in the contexts of social and cultural themes that are being engaged within the game jams. It’s a way to really think about their power and involvement in addressing the most difficult challenges of our time, from climate change to mental health to questions around democracy.”

- CHI facilitator, Hilversum (CHI)

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Through cultural storytelling and world-building, the participants of the CGJ had the opportunity to reimagine heritage narratives and values. By embedding cultural themes into their prototypes, they explored and experimented with how heritage could be interpreted and represented in contemporary, game forms. Some participants noted that the process deepened their understanding of cultural topics, while others expressed excitement about using games as an engaging medium for cultural dialogue.

“It makes youth think a bit more deeply about it. It’s a different way of thinking about a game and experiencing a game, also in the making process. We got a showing of the museum, and it really made us think about the game and incorporate what we just learned and saw in a way that we wouldn’t have if it weren’t specifically cultural based. That was cool.”

- Game Jam participant, Aarhus (YC)

Creativity was also activated by the real-world contexts foregrounded in D3.3 in principle 5 (real-world Cultural Hubs), indicating that imagination unfolded inside inspiring cultural spaces – such as museums, libraries, town streets and archives – where the physical environment itself acted as a cultural-creative stimulus. Many participants spoke about how the environments they visited, such as their walks through the town centre of Óbidos or the artwalks in the exhibitions at ARoS Art Museum, inspired them to incorporate specific heritage storylines in their games or to explore new storytelling techniques and game designs. These immersive experiences, therefore, demonstrated how cultural spaces can act as a catalyst for imaginative thinking: as the participants reimaged historical and cultural narratives, the cultural themes of the game jams fuelled their creativity.

“One of the most important things when having game jams generally is that you create a platform for youth to tell their stories. And when you encourage people in that way and give them that agency, you also spark a new sense of trust and creativity. And I think that’s really important when telling a story. [...] Especially for Cultural Game Jams, you’re having this great production process in a cultural space like Aarhus or a museum and there’s inspiration everywhere when you’re creating a game.”

- YAB member, Aarhus (YC)

Moreover, principle 4 in D3.3 and D4.2 (co-creation for public good(s)) also further strengthened creativity by grounding it in shared cultural values: participants were not simply making games, but they were collectively shaping cultural narratives and generating public meaning through game design, which led to a richer interpretation of cultural heritage.

“What motivated us to participate in the EPIC-WE project was largely related to our role as Cultural Heritage Institution, the vast collection of public broadcasting material we have, our radio archive, and a whole variety of Dutch media heritage. As an institution, we’re constantly looking for ways to share that history and share that material with other people, and finding creative ways to show its contemporary value. Teaming up with EPIC-WE was a great opportunity to illustrate how youth can reflect on their historical meaning and also refract that meaning into the present by engaging with these different social and cultural themes that are part of the game jam. And really taking them as inspiration for the games that they’re developing.”

- CHI stakeholder, Hilversum (CHI)

However, engagement with cultural heritage was not uniform across all CGJs and participant experiences. Some struggled to connect cultural themes to their game concepts, while others experienced uncertainty about how to translate heritage into gameplay in meaningful ways. Time pressure within certain formats occasionally constrained creative flow, limiting the opportunity to properly integrate cultural heritage and values or refine ideas. These challenges highlight the importance of cultural mediation, structured reflection, and proper pacing and methods as found in the CGJ Kit – confirming that creativity flourishes when participants have adequate scaffolding, time and support to explore cultural material at depth.

Playfulness & fun

A defining feature of the CGJs is the playful atmosphere, and many participants did describe their experience as enjoyable and fun, even when faced with certain challenges:

“If I could create an environment that actually stimulates them to do awesome things and feel good about it, like, I'd be, like, a winner.”

- CHI facilitator, Hilversum (CHI)

Warm-up activities, LEGO challenges, and guided heritage walks created a joyful atmosphere:

“When asked, some of the group found the exercise of the LEGO tower fun and it sparked self-reflection on the importance of each other's roles within the team.”

- Researcher, Hilversum (HEI)

“I enjoyed playing with Lego, like just being a little child for a second, you know. That probably wasn't at the point, but yeah. I completely forgot about the challenges. A little team-building exercise. Yeah, that was definitely fun.”

- Game Jam participant, Hilversum (YC)

The combination of structured activities in the CGJ Kit and open-ended creative freedom allowed participants to experiment and develop ideas in ways that felt engaging rather than rigid or inhibiting. This is also key to fostering deeper heritage learning moments, as participants are not simply absorbing information but actively embodying it in real-time. This reflects principles 1 and 3 in D3.2 and D4.1: the CGJ Kit along with all three CGJ formats (Focused, Flexible and Freeform) supported the playful exploration, while the environments of the CGJs cultivated curiosity and creative engagement.

Fun played a crucial role in the learning process, to help and sustain motivation, as well as to create a sense of togetherness among the YCs. It was not a superficial element. It played a role to ease the participants of the CGJs into challenging conversations about cultural heritage, values and identity. Moreover, activities such as a pizza-night and guided tours maintained motivation under time pressure and acted as bonding moments between participants. In this way, playfulness helped to sustain energy across the various CGJ formats, making the creative process and cultural engagement more sustainable.

“They are having fun, though, and talking and discussing together and are - as such - enjoying the process.”

- Researcher, Aarhus (HEI)

“The best experience also was that pizza in the middle of the night. Definitely the greatest experience. The greatest experience. We were so tired after the whole day and so confused with all of our topics which we wanted to solve and then pizza just solved all of them for us. Everybody just did their work at night.”

- Game Jam participant, Hilversum (YC)

It also seemed that – despite the challenges – the collaborative energy, combined with the improvisational nature of the activities also made the YCs feel proud and satisfied at the end:

“You know, it was crazy. It was messy. But we just knew we were going to do it. And we did it. And it was impressive. It was an impressive one. And then we [got] feedback from the experts, which was useful for us to progress to the next phase. And then, like, going through that, you know, prototyping, testing again. Yeah, with little resources, little time, little sleep. But coming up with something at the end of the day.”

- Game Jam participant, Hilversum (YC)

This suggests that Cultural Game Jams benefit from formats that balance between structured exercises and free creative time, ensuring that participants have the space to develop ideas organically while still staying engaged.

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In short, playfulness supported creative agency, social cohesion, and cultural meaning-making, confirming the CGJs as playful yet deeply meaningful spaces of cultural participation.

Collaboration & co-creation

Collaboration was foundational to the CGJ experience. Teams composed of youth with different backgrounds, skills, experiences and interests had to work together to create playable cultural game prototypes under time pressure. This-co-creative dynamic reflects Principle 4 in D3.2 and D4.1, to cultivate an “Epic we”, where participants engage in shared cultural creation, as well as Principle 1, where adaptable CGJ formats support different modes of collaborative organisation. Co-creation required communication, negotiation, compromise and collective decision making, which are core skills in any cultural innovation process.

The autonomy granted to YCs to form their own teams was an important element of the Cultural Game Jam activity, encouraging peer-driven collaboration. However, as the analyses illustrate, this autonomy did sometimes introduce certain tensions. For example, D2.3 identified recurrent cross-hub challenges – including overloaded documentation, skill asymmetries, and venue shifts – which shape participants’ experience of collaboration. Moreover, D4.3 notices that by prioritising friendships over the actual task of game development, some participants may have inadvertently limited the potential for diverse creative contributions. The decision to place social bonds at the forefront of team formation reflects a natural inclination to seek comfort in familiar relationships. But in a co-creation setting, this approach can sometimes potentially undermine the effectiveness of collaboration, as individuals may not fully engage with the task or may rely too heavily on the other team members to carry the group effort.

“It was hard being the only stranger in a group of friends and the only queer person in a group of straight men.”

- YAB member (YC)

“In two of the three classes the students had difficulty focusing and there was a lot of chatting, specifically during the explanation and discussion moments as a group. The idea was that the students would create their own groups based on the games that were available and they would like to play the most. In practice, many of the students based their group's choice on being with their friends over a game they liked. The students were told at the end that the groups they were playing the games in would also be the teams they would create a game with during the game jam.”

- Researcher, Hilversum (HEI)

While autonomy and voice are vital for fostering engagement, the analysis in D4.1 suggests that, in some cases (for instance, when the participants already know each other beforehand), a more structured approach to team formation might reduce some of the challenges identified. This could encourage the participants to work with a wider range of peers, potentially promoting a more balanced distribution and involvement across the group. Such an approach could also offer students the opportunity to develop new interpersonal skills and broaden their collaborative experience. Challenges such as disengagement, unbalanced contributions, and the dominance of social relationships highlight important lessons for future group work initiatives.

“Group dynamics are difficult. Some teams are fine, some have a few teammates who are unmotivated, but slow down the process. It is not clear whether in some

groups specific students might be interested in being more active, but are held back due to group dynamics. Perhaps instead of friends together in a team a more random approach would be preferred for this age group."

- Researcher, Hilversum (HEI)

The suggestion that was raised by a HEI researcher that friendships might hinder optimal collaboration presents an interesting paradox: the very bonds that can make collaboration and teamwork enjoyable and comforting may, in some cases, distract from the task's creative potential. Challenges such as difficulty focusing and off-topic chatting are reflective of how personal dynamics can shape the collaboration process, often influencing both social cohesion and the effectiveness of the collaboration of a team.

However, it is also important not to overlook the many positive moments observed and the broader realities of co-creation in collaborative environments. Although pre-formed friend groups, uneven skill levels, or unclear roles sometimes created some tensions or uncertainties during the CGJs, these tensions also revealed how collaboration is not effortless, but requires the right facilitation, trust and shared responsibility from all stakeholders involved. Moreover, working together on creative projects not only fostered teamwork, but also a sense of belonging and group cohesion, and the participants showed eagerness for collaborative engagement:

"The high school students were very attentive to the workshop, and asked some questions that their teacher, Diogo, who was giving the workshop, thought were very pertinent. The Lusofona students seemed to be very immersed in the task and organized themselves quite quickly. It was clear that they came with their groups already defined and also with some ideas for the game, which could be

related to the fact that they had already had contact with the topic at two different times.”

- Researcher, Óbidos (HEI)

The participants experienced moments of connection and shared effort. Whether through the experience of creating a game together, the common challenges faced in the design process, or having to present their projects together, many participants shared that they enjoyed sharing thoughts with people from different disciplines, backgrounds, and perspectives.

“I had a feeling that it was lovely meeting across disciplines and perspectives. At some point, I drew a square on a post-its, and later it blew from the table to the floor. Even later that day some of the group members saw it, picked it up and were excited with potential ideas stemming from the simple drawing - and it created a nice experience of learning from each other’s perspectives.”

- Game Jam participant, Aarhus (YC)

Overall, it seems they put in great effort to reinforce the collective spirit, combining their individual skills and expertise to create something meaningful within a short timeframe, which is central to the concept of CGJs and co-creation.

“I would say that creating our team was pretty surprising because we didn't know each other and we just came to one room and because we were sitting next to each other, we just decided to combine teams. And in the end, as it turned out, we were a great team.”

- *Game Jam participant, Hilversum (YC)*

Collaboration was also a foundational experience to the wider Quadruple Helix ecosystem, as it extended beyond the YCs teams during the interactions of the CGJs. All the QH stakeholders co-designed formats together, adapted facilitation strategies, and reflected together on what was and was not working during earlier iterations. CHIs provided cultural and historical grounding, HEIs supported methodological rigour, CIs contributed technical and creative expertise and YCs shaped the content through their lived experiences of the GCJs and their worldviews.

"The approach to this project was very different from what we normally do. [...] We have all the stakeholders to ideate together and start sketching up the first prototypes, and then we end up having the project built with everyone's contribution. [...] You get immediate results because you can see the reactions and then have on-site discussions and immediately react to what's happening. It's a very agile way of developing the project. [...] This project can prove that we can work together with stakeholders directly on location and find the results that make everyone happy."

- *Creative Industries stakeholder, Óbidos (CI)*

"This project helps us game designers to look beyond just the design process. It helps us look at our design and say 'Why are we making it? Have other people done it before? How does it look in art? Is there some kind of connection to a social structure or how does this specific generation feel about it?' Instead of just jumping on an idea and doing that, it forces us to be really cerebral and really analyse what we're doing. I think that's extremely valuable."

- *Game Designer, Aarhus (CI)*

D3.3's QH principles are amplified in this dynamic. Principle 1 (democratising cultural innovation) positioned YCs not as learners but as active co-creators with CHIs, CIs, and HEIs. Principle 2 (transformative partnerships) meant that collaboration was reciprocal, with all stakeholders learning from each other and being open to change during the iterative process of organising and facilitating the CGJs. Principle 3 (meeting in the middle) demanded shared vocabularies, common ground and willingness to translate across various disciplinaries, as well as generational and institutional differences.

“There was sort of this magical connection between everything. The innovation ecosystem was a very fruitful tool for me to understand the potential of what we could do, and to see how we could create this meeting place between industry, young people, educational environments, research and cultural heritage sites. There was this valuable intersection between them. It became this melting pot where everything changed because of each other, and it influenced each other in a very nice way, And I think it allowed us to think about how this could be used in other venues or other sectors as well. You could also do this at a traditional museum about local history, or you could do it in a hospital... you can really use these tools that were made into the game jams in other sectors as well.”

- *Project manager, Aarhus (CI)*

Ultimately, collaboration in the CGJs did not simply produce games, it produced new relationships, understanding, and collective cultural agency, demonstrating the full potential of the Quadruple Helix, Cultural Hub, and Cultural Game Jam approach.

Empowerment Participation

Empowered participation was a defining element of EPIC-WE, reflecting the project's commitment to democratise cultural innovation and position youth citizens as equal partners within the Quadruple Helix Ecosystem, Cultural Hubs, and Cultural Game Jams. Rather than being passive recipients of cultural content, young participants were invited to take on active, visible, and meaningful roles across the entire process – from ideation and game design, to decision-making and public presentation. This directly aligns with D3.3 Principle 6 (Advancing Empowered Participation in Culture), which emphasises co-ownership, agency and equitable involvement as core components of cultural innovation.

“They are actively taking on different roles as designer, coder, artist, gamemaster, etc., which becomes even more apparent when they are met with constructive criticism from the experts and other participants.”

- *Researcher, Aarhus (HEI)*

“During the creation of this project, I coordinated several steps and decisions when our team was starting to lose focus.”

- *Game Jam participant, Óbidos (YC)*

Across all hubs, YCs demonstrated a strong sense of ownership over their ideas and creative direction. They independently negotiated themes, shaped game concepts, delegated team roles and made design decisions. The open structure of the CGJs – supported by the CFJ Kit and its tools such as the Ideation Wheel and Expert Council – provided a flexible environment in which the YCs could develop confidence, voice

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and agency. Moments such as public showcases or presenting their cultural game prototypes at the public EXPO, pitching to experts, or offering peer feedback served as important milestones that reinforced their role as cultural co-creators rather than only participants in a predefined activity.

“The creative processes of the game jam that I liked were the more extended process and the loose and open approach.”

- Game Jam participant, Aarhus (YC)

“We had a lot of freedom which was really beneficial for our games, having the freedom to go out when we wanted and take breaks helps me keep a cool head”

- Game Jam participant, Óbidos (YC)

This dynamic is deeply connected to Principle 2 in D3.2 and D4.1 (Aim for cultural participation, co-creation and empowerment), which positions game-making as a cultural method enabling youth to get a sense of ownership and belonging, and allowing them to express their lived experiences, identity, values and imagination. Across hubs, YCs used game design not only as a (technical) activity, but as a form of cultural authorship, exploring societal themes, reinterpreting heritage and articulating their own perspectives on contemporary issues.

“Games are playful and engaging, and therefore they afford participatory modes of communication that might meet the needs of some audiences. We can bring a broad appeal to some of the positively speaking “nerdy” academic stuff that permeates how we talk about art in museums, and offer a tone of voice that is more inclusive.”

- *Project leader, Aarhus (CHI)*

The empowered participation observed during the CGJs was also relational and systemic. In line with Principle 2 of D3.3 (Equal and transformative partnerships), YCs worked alongside CHIs, CIs, and HEIs as co-equals, challenging traditional hierarchies. Youth Advisory Board (YAB) members further extended this empowerment by contributing to planning meetings, facilitation of later CGJs and evaluation processes. Their involvement illustrated how empowered participation is strengthened when YCs are trusted with responsibility and included in structural decision-making processes.

For some participants, this was a transformative experience, realising that their voices and ideas had value within a larger cultural dialogue. This empowerment was particularly evident in moments where participants took the lead in discussions, problem-solving, or creative decision-making. By working within teams and seeing their ideas come to life, they gained confidence in their abilities to contribute to collaborative projects. A significant positive outcome of the CGJs was the sense of empowerment that participants experienced. Many found that the open-ended nature of the CGJs allowed them to take ownership and agency of their ideas, express their creativity, and engage in meaningful decision-making. Unlike traditional learning environments where young people are often passive recipients of information, the CGJs positioned them as active creators of games and culture. These findings also align with D2.3's insights into youth empowerment and value creation (RQ3), where empowerment emerges when youth are recognised as cultural agents rather than just learners.

At the same time, empowered participation revealed important complexities. Some participants experienced uncertainty when navigating open-ended creative tasks or

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lack of hierarchy, showing that some participants needed more mediation or scaffolding to fully step into co-ownership.

“I think, at least from what I felt, it was that I could give more value to the theme imposed on our work and also realise that it wasn't as limiting as I thought, that we could explore it at a better level and that we had various paths to follow, not as narrow as the theme was presented at the university.”

- Game Jam participant, Óbidos (YC)

Balancing the autonomy of YCs with the CGJ Kit and supportive guidance from facilitators was a key lesson that emerged within the CGJs. Nevertheless, the CGJs did demonstrate that – especially when YCs were given space, trust and opportunities to choose their own themes, interpret heritage materials and guide their own design direction – they developed a pronounced sense of agency, confidence and belonging within cultural innovation. In this way, empowered participation became not just an outcome, but a method: an evolving practice of shared authority, collaboration and cultural authorship that lies at the heart of the EPIC-WE vision.

“CGJs are a great way of allowing people to have a voice. Especially where they are otherwise muted. Games as cultural and games as heritage is an important and underprioritised aspect of game culture. EPIC-WE makes it abundantly clear that all of a sudden we can look at games as art, as poems, and as a new way of thinking, seeing and imagining things.”

- Researcher, Aarhus (HEI)

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A core component of empowered participation across all Cultural Hubs was the commitment to inclusive practices. The CGJs were intentionally designed to enable participation from young people with diverse backgrounds, interests, abilities and levels of experience, reducing barriers to access by offering free events, providing supportive facilitation, and valuing multiple forms of cultural knowledge and creative expression. Inclusivity was also embedded in team dynamics: facilitators and mentors paid attention to equitable voice distribution, creating spaces where quieter or less experienced youth could contribute meaningfully and influence decision-making. This aligns with the project's broader aim of ensuring that cultural innovation is not limited to highly skilled or already confident participants but actively empowers those who are often underrepresented in cultural and creative sectors. Through these inclusive approaches, the CGJs strengthened young people's sense of belonging and ensured that empowered participation extended beyond decision-making structures to encompass who gets to participate, how they participate, and whose perspectives shape the outcomes.

Beyond individual agency within the CGJs itself, empowered participation was also structurally supported through the creation of Youth Advisory Boards (YABs) in all three Cultural Hubs. As described in D4.1, the YABs were established to ensure that youth were not only participants in the CGJs, but active partners with a formal role in shaping the project's direction and decision-making processes. YAB members contributed to meetings, advised on executions of CGJs, and were given defined roles such as co-facilitators, observers, jurors, or researchers. This aligns directly with Principle 6 in D3.3, which emphasises that empowered participation requires young people to be treated as genuine co-owners within the Quadruple Helix ecosystem rather than end-users or consultees. Over the course of the project, the YAB model evolved into a sustainable mechanism for youth influence and empowerment. This structural embedding of YCs' perspectives significantly strengthened the depth of empowered participation observed in the GCJs.

Social connections

The CGJs showed to be a highly effective format for fostering meaningful social connections among youth participants, as well as between YCs and the other QH stakeholders. These social dynamics emerged naturally from the collaborative, playful and culturally rich environments of the CGJs. Participants engaged in shared cultural-creative idea-generating, and co-designing sessions, which strengthened interpersonal bonds and helped build a sense of belonging. Many participants highlighted both the social value of the jam and indicated they appreciated the opportunity to meet new people and build a sense of community through shared cultural-creative work. This directly resonates with Principle 4 of D4.1 (Cultivate an “Epic we”), which frames CGJs as spaces where collective creativity extends beyond individual contribution. Across Cultural Hubs, moments of intense teamwork, shared game-making and culture-making, peer feedback and collaborative playtesting generated a strong sense of unity.

The development of social connections was also shaped by the cross-sectoral structure of the QH culturalhub model. In accordance with Principle 1 of D3.3 (Democratising Cultural Innovation), the CGJs created opportunities for young people to interact with cultural professionals, game designers, researchers, and educators in informal and equal ways. This flattened the hierarchy and enabled authentic interaction, making participants’ voices feel recognised and valued. Conversations with curators or receiving feedback from experts all contributed to a rich, relational cultural learning environment.

“The youth get to know professionals from a lot of different fields, not only facilitators and researchers in the archive, but also from their own university, from the research environment, from the creative industries... they received a lot

of different relational inputs both in terms of people they meet that are from the consortium and their peers, so people they work with."

- Researcher, Hilversum (HEI)

Furthermore, Principle 3 of D3.3 (Meeting in the middle) played an important role in shaping social connections. Since the CGJs brought together individuals with different skill levels, backgrounds, ages, genders, and disciplinary vocabularies, both the YCs as well as the HEIs, CIs and CHIs had to negotiate common ground. This encourages openness, empathy and collaborative problem-solving, deepening interpersonal connections and fostering a shared language in relation to cultural heritage and game development. In many cases, the youth participants expressed appreciation for meeting peers from different disciplines and backgrounds and forming new connections.

"So my favourite part was connecting with youth and also what the project stands for, which is cultural games, fun, but also the part of integrated culture and integrating youth."

- YAB member & Game Jam participant, Óbidos (YCs)

"It was very fun and nice to meet a lot of new people. I really liked the people that I met and I made a lot of new friends. I think that's why others should also try this Cultural Game Jam. Both if you've made games before and also if you haven't. It's a great way to meet new people and make new friends."

- Game Jam participant, Aarhus (YC)

Playfulness, fun and shared cultural-creative challenges also contributed significantly to social cohesion. Warm-up activities, group exercises, museum tours, and even informal moments such as shared meals created low-stake opportunities for interaction. These activities supported a relaxed atmosphere in which social barriers were diminished and collaborative energy grew, reinforcing the social dimension of cultural participation.

Overall, the CGJs functioned as socially connective cultural experiences for all stakeholders involved. They created spaces where youth could forge new friendships and creative partnerships around cultural heritage, but also create cross-sector relationships with HEIs, CHIs and CIs. These connections not only supported collaborative game-making, but also enhanced the participants' sense of belonging, cultural engagement, and collective identity within the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Ecosystem.

“The friendships that are made and strengthened.”

- HEI researcher, Observation Grid, Aarhus (HEI)

2.3 Assessing Impact: What it takes to Game Jam with Culture

The 12 CGJs in Aarhus, Hilversum and Óbidos fostered a meaningful youth engagement with cultural heritage, enabling participants to explore values, identity and cultural narratives through hands-on creative practice. They demonstrated that meaningful cultural and societal impact arises not from a single method or activity, but from the interplay of several dimensions that shape how stakeholders learn,

create, collaborate and connect. Across all Cultural Hubs, the indicators established in WP6 provide a clear picture of what it takes for a Cultural Game Jam to become a space of empowered participation and cultural innovation:

1. **Cultural Game Jams require cultural grounding.** Impact emerged when participants engaged directly with heritage collections, local stories, artworks, archives and townscapes. Cultural input serves both as inspiration, shared reference and game-making material, enabling youth to reinterpret cultural heritage and values rather than merely consume them. CGJs therefore need accessible, sensory, and guided encounters with culture - such as the CGJ Kit - to support deeper knowledge and cultural understanding.
2. **CGJs function as intensive cultural learning laboratories.** Participants develop technical, creative, communicative and reflective skills through cultural game prototyping, iteration and teamwork. Impact is strongest when facilitators scaffold learning with clear processes and methods without constraining imagination, enabling youth with varied backgrounds to contribute meaningfully. Cross-sector collaboration among YCs, HEIs, CHIs and CIs strengthens this skills ecosystem.
3. **Creativity flourishes when participants are given space** to explore ideas freely, grounded in cultural heritage material they can remix and reinterpret. The CGJ format and its CGJ Kit – with divergent and convergent phases – supports creative risk-taking and cultural experimentation. Creativity requires

an environment that balances inspiration with agency, offering cultural tools and methods while allowing youth to define their narrative directions.

4. **Play is not something superficial**, it was the driver for youth participation, motivation and cultural exploration. Activities such as warm-ups, guided heritage walks, and collaborative CGJ challenges helped ease social tension, build trust, and sustain engagement under time pressure. Playfulness enables learning to unfold organically, supporting both experimentation and comfort.

5. **Co-creation lies at the centre** of EPIC-WE's Quadruple Helix model. CGJs work when diverse participants meet in the middle to negotiate ideas, share responsibilities and collectively shape outcomes. Balanced facilitation is essential: teams benefit from agency, but also from gentle structuring so that their tasks become clear. Impact is strongest when collaboration is not simply seen as teamwork, but as a shared cultural authorship across youth, institutions and creative actors.

6. **Empowered participation is a defining impact of the CGJs**. Participants feel ownership and empowerment when they are invited to shape decisions, contribute meaningfully to the CGJs and can share their ideas with other experts and peers. Empowered participation requires a redistribution of authority: facilitators, CHIs, HEIs and CIs must meet in the middle, validating youth insights as cultural knowledge. In this project, this dimension has been specifically strengthened by involving a Youth Advisory Board.

7. **CGJs generate new cultural relationships, networks and shared identities.**

Trust and belonging emerged as critical conditions for productive co-creation. Social cohesion often determined the quality of collaboration and the depth of cultural heritage engagement within the game prototypes. Impact grows when CGJs intentionally cultivate welcoming atmospheres, inclusive team dynamics and opportunities for social bonding around cultural heritage.

Overall, the CGJs functioned as catalysts for cultural creativity, collaboration, and youth empowerment, demonstrating that game-making can operate as a powerful mode of culture-making across diverse European contexts. What's interesting is that the impact of EPIC-WE's interventions cannot be reduced to simple success or failure. Instead, it reveals a complex, evolving landscape where opportunities and challenges coexist. In sum, what it takes to Game Jam with Culture is not simply time, tools or templates, but a carefully balanced ecosystem that integrates cultural inspiration, co-creative methods, youth agency, playful exploration and supportive environments. The seven impact indicators collectively illustrate how CGJs operate as transformative cultural experiences, enabling youth and institutional partners to create, imagine and learn together with cultural heritage and across the Quadruple Helix ecosystem.

Evaluation

03

3. Evaluation

This section marks the Evaluation Phase of the Europeana Playbook. The evidence and data gathered and analysed during WP4 is interpreted using the indicator framework developed in WP6. The preceding impact narrative and the synthesis in section 3.4 together constitute the evaluation, identifying the extent and nature of change generated by the CGJs across the three hubs.

3.1 Evaluation of Indicators

The seven indicators applied in this deliverable provided a clear and structured framework for interpreting the outcomes of the CGJs. Overall, they proved to be well aligned with the activities and experiences documented throughout the project, and they effectively captured the main areas of change observed across the hubs. Their strength lies in their ability to synthesise diverse qualitative materials into a coherent assessment of cultural learning, creativity and youth engagement.

At the same time, it is important to note that some indicators were slightly more difficult to measure than others, given that supporting analyses were based on qualitative data rather than quantitative data. Therefore, while the impact indicators provided a valuable framework for assessing the CGJs, they may not have fully captured the full span of participants' experiences. Some aspects of engagement, such as spontaneous moments of connection, shifting group dynamics, or the fluid nature of creativity, do not always align neatly with predefined indicators. Moreover, the way participants framed their experiences may not have directly mirrored the language of our indicators, even when those elements were present. It is important to keep this in mind. Moreover, the Evaluation Phase revealed potential areas of

refinement. While the seven indicators presented in this report capture the core dimensions of impact, over the course of the project, some partners noted additional aspects that might merit separate indicators in future iterations. Taken together, the indicators did provide a solid and sufficient flexible framework, but they also highlight the need for ongoing development of impact measurement in participatory cultural innovation contexts.

3.2 Evaluation of Impact across Indicators

Assessing the findings across all twelve Cultural Game Jams demonstrates that impact emerged consistently across most indicators, though with varying degrees of intensity and evidence. *Knowledge & Cultural Understanding* showed clear impact across all Cultural Hubs and CGJs: participants engaged deeply with cultural heritage materials and demonstrated the ability to reinterpret cultural narratives through game-making. *Creativity & Imagination* and *Skills Development* were also strongly represented, with participants producing diverse games through/for culture concepts, experimenting with various materials, and developing teamwork, communication and design capacities.

The evidence for *Empowered Participation* was particularly significant where Youth Advisory Boards were active. Youth reported increased agency, ownership and empowerment in shaping both content and process, confirming the strengthened role of the fourth helix within the Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs. *Collaboration & Co-creation* also emerged strongly across all Cultural Hubs and CGJ sites, both between the YCs themselves who proved to be strong collaborators and co-creators during the CGJs, but also in moments where facilitation intentionally supported balanced team dynamics and equitable voice distribution during the CGJ iterations.

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Evidence for *Social Connections* and *Playfulness & Fun* was present but more context-dependent. Nonetheless, these indicators were clearly observed in team interactions, collective idea-generation and problem-solving, and testimonials, and they contributed meaningfully to participants' motivation, sense of belonging, and positive engagement with cultural material.

Overall, the evaluation across indicators shows that the Cultural Game Jams generated multidimensional impact, with particularly strong evidence for cultural understanding, creativity, skills and empowered participation.

Methodology

04

4. Methodology

This report builds on the analytical and methodological foundations established in D2.3, D3.2, D3.3, D4.1 and D4.2. EPIC-WE operates through a Quadruple Helix model, where Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education, and Youth collaborate as equal partners in co-creation. The Cultural Game Jam served as living laboratories, testing and refining the Cultural Game Jam Framework (Janssen, M., 2025, Quadruple Helix Operationalisation). The term “Game Jam” refers to events that are “similar to a hackathon where people come together for a short period of time to create games”, often with a central theme explained to the participants in the beginning. (Kultima et al., 2020) These events can provide an opportunity to socialize, network, develop skills and experiment with creativity; supporting the development of soft skills. (Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K. (2024); Germaine N. and Healy, J. P., 2023). The project employs a primary focus on qualitative methods to assess its impact due to the complex nature of European values, cultural heritage, and youth engagement. The Impact Assessment process, which is mainly based on the European Impact Playbook, includes four key phases: *design*, *assessment*, *impact narration*, and *evaluation*. Each phase feeds into the next, ensuring continuous learning and adaptation. While the Europeana Impact Playbook provided an initial framework for assessing impact, in this context it was adapted to fit EPIC-WE’s participatory and iterative nature. The impact indicators, therefore, translate the Quadruple Helix, Cultural Hubs and Cultural Game Jam principles as stated in D3.2 and D3.3 into practice, focusing on how cultural innovation unfolds through empowerments, collaboration, and real-world participation. This report further aligns with the analytical insights produced in D2.3, which synthesises evidence from twelve CGJs across Aarhus, Hilversum and Óbidos. D2.3 provides detailed insights into lessons learned from design interventions and collaborations, facilitation practices, youth participation and empowerment, and cultural integration

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and transformation, as well as the theoretical, analytical, and methodological outcomes of the project that are vital elements in creating new conditions for and enabling empowered participation. Incorporating these insights ensures that the impact assessment presented in D6.4 remains grounded in the research results and empirical realities of both local and glocal interventions, including the challenges related to documentation, disciplinary asymmetries, and the embedding of EU values in game mechanics (see D2.3, RQ1–RQ3).

Use of the Europeana Impact Playbook as a methodological framework

The Europeana Impact Playbook was adopted as the primary methodological framework for structuring the EPIC-WE impact assessment, because it aligns directly with the cultural, participatory and multi-stakeholder ambitions of the project. The Playbook's *Change Pathway* provides a sector-specific model for analysing how cultural heritage activities generate social, cultural and economic impact through a sequence of internal resources activities, outputs, outcomes and long-term changes. This mirrors the project's impact structure, which distinguishes between immediate results, medium-term effects and long-term societal and economic impacts. Moreover, it encourages participatory reflection, iterative prototyping, and cross-disciplinary collaboration, which are all core tenets of the EPIC-WE project as well (Europeana Playbook, [The Europeana Impact Playbook: a history and guiding principles](#)).

As EPIC-WE is grounded in Design-Based Research within a Quadruple Helix Ecosystem (CHI, HEI, CI and YC) that meet in the middle in Cultural Hubs to organise and run Cultural Game Jams, the playbook's emphasis on participatory impact identification, stakeholder-specific change pathways and qualitative evidence collection is particularly suited to the project's co-creative methodology. The CGJs

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rely heavily on collaborative learning, creativity, cultural engagement and youth empowerment – all impact areas that the Europeana framework is explicitly designed to capture.

Moreover, the Playbook supports a narrative approach that fits with EPIC-WE's interdisciplinary and iterative approach, providing tools such as the Narrative Arc, which was used to transform qualitative and quantitative findings from D2.3, D4.1 and D4.2 into a coherent impact story. This approach enables EPIC-WE to produce an impact narrative that is both evidence-based and accessible for CHIs, CIs, HEIs and policy stakeholders.

Finally, adopting this established European cultural impact methodology strengthens the replicability and transferability objectives of EPIC-WE, as it ensures that the impact assessment process can be later adapted into a public impact measurement guide (D6.5), supporting CHIs, CIs and HEIs across Europe in implementing EPIC-WE's game-making as culture-making framework using a recognised cultural-sector tool.

Overall, the Europeana Playbook provides the methodological scaffolding for evaluating the cultural, social, and educational outcomes of the CGJs. It complements our project by offering reflection tools that can be used to capture learning processes during and after the CGJs. The Playbook's participatory ethos aligns with the Quadruple Helix Ecosystem and the project's principles, as it...

- ...encourages co-definition of success criteria among all helices.
- ...captures qualitative transformations (e.g. skills, awareness, belonging) through a narrative methodology.
- ...supports transferability by translating local reflections into reusable templates.

Alternative methodologies (e.g. traditional impact logic models) were considered but deemed less suited, because they emphasise linear causality over participatory transformation. This project's goal is not to measure causal change, but to trace iterative empowerment and cultural learning in a qualitative way.

4.1 Overview

The methodology for the T6.1 impact assessment follows a multi-layered, participatory approach aimed at building capacity and delivering policy recommendations for the cultural, creative, and educational sectors. It also involves three levels of design: macro, meso, and micro, focusing on fostering cultural innovation and transformation as the multi-layered aspect. The participatory approach of the methodology comes directly from the organised CGJs, where the participants (youth), organizers and observers provided their remarks, observations and feedback throughout the events.

Figure 7: Three levels of design

These levels, as presented above in Figure 2, are structured around the *EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem (QH)*, the *EPIC-WE Cultural Hub Model*, and the *EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams (CGJs)*, respectively.

On the macro level, the QH adds the fourth helix of “the public” to the ecosystem, involving representatives or participants from all partners forming the helix: public authorities and organizations, industry, academia, and citizens (Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K. (2024)). Carayannis and Campbell (2022) state that the QH ecosystem emphasizes the authentic inclusion of the fourth helix, which relates to the ‘media-based and culture-based public,’ ‘civil society,’ ‘arts, artistic research, and arts-based innovation,’ as well as the overarching theme of ‘democracy and knowledge democracy’. Translated into EPIC-WE’s framework, the project aims to structure and implement an iterative adjustment of a QH ecosystem, tailored for culture and the

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empowered participation between the QH actors, and bringing the youth as the fourth helix to the system, across three sites in Europe through Cultural Hubs and CGJs (Somers Miles, R., et al. (2024), [D3.1 Protocol 3](#); Koppelman, W., & Lennaerts, K. (2024), [D3.1 Protocol 4](#)).

Figure 8: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem (Taratori et al., 2021)

On the meso level, supported by Brandt and Bruun's (2023) as well as others, through adaptation of the format into 'Ethnographic Living Labs' in the city, EPIC-WE engages in a similar adaptation and transformation of the Living Labs (LLs) concept into Cultural Hubs (CHs) and focuses on QH co-creation of research and innovation in the form of cultural value, experiences, knowledges, and formats for empowered participation in culture, cultural heritage, culture-making within CHs and through CGJs. This structure positions the QH partners as research and innovation partners simultaneously. Each partner brings specific knowledge, methods, and practices to the middle as ways of approaching research and innovation within the domain of

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culture. In the CHs, the QH partners work together as co-creators of culture, cultural heritage and new futures in culture and society.

On the micro level, the CGJs are employed as a way for QH partners to establish transformative partnerships that work together to ideate cultural worlds and environments that enable new forms of engagement, participation, belonging and co-creation within the cultural domain. When brought together, the EPIC-WE framework on the macro, meso, and micro levels specifies how CHI, CI, HEI, and YC can work together as partners in cultural-creative innovation and transformation (Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K. (2024), D3.2: Protocol 1, p. 49).

Figure 9: EPIC-WE QH Ecosystem

4.2 The Europeana Playbook

Since EPIC-WE employs a primary focus on qualitative methods to assess its impact due to the complex nature of European values, cultural heritage, and youth engagement, we decided to use the [Europeana Impact Playbook](#) as a guideline for our impact evaluation. The Europeana Playbook has been specifically designed to help cultural heritage institutions assess the impact of their activities and emphasises that measuring impact “is not a one-off action, but a flexible and ongoing process that can benefit from in the long-term as you embed impact thinking in your processes and organisational culture¹”. The Playbook offers a framework to operationalise impact measurement actions and consists of several phases – which are explained [in detail on the website](#) (and will also be explained below in context of our CGJs) – to follow impact design, impact measurement, impact narration & evaluation. Taking this structured approach will be of great value in the EPIC-WE process where the variables differ per Cultural Hub context and CGJ theme.

Each Cultural Hub operates as a living laboratory for the QH model. Within these Cultural Hubs, the CIs, CHIs, HEIs and YCs co-create new cultural practices (Janssen, M., 2025, Quadruple Helix Operationalisation). This ecosystem ensures that the Youth Citizens (YCs) participate as equal partners rather than end users or beneficiaries. The Cultural Hubs function as “meeting-in-the-middle” spaces, where academic, educational, creative, cultural and civic perspectives intersect and where the voices of all stakeholders are acknowledged and shared. Impact is therefore assessed not only through outcomes, but through the quality of collaboration and reflexivity observed among the Quadruple Helix Ecosystem of this project. This playbook approach is, therefore, not an external add-on, but a pragmatic expression

¹<https://europeana.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/CB/pages/2256863617/Introduction+-+everything+you+need+to+know+about+the+Impact+Playbook>

(similar to the DBR approach used in CGJ interventions), which includes four key phases: *impact design*, *impact measurement*, *impact narration*, and *evaluation*. Each phase feeds into the next, ensuring continuous learning and adaptation.

Figure 10: [Phases of impact assessment](#) (Europeana Playbook)

These four phases have been incorporated in our current impact assessment, which will be further explained below:

Phase 1: Design

Stakeholder Identification and Needs Analysis

The design phase involved identifying key stakeholders across three levels:

- **Macro level:** CIs, CHIs, HEIs and Youth.

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- **Meso level:** The development of Cultural Hubs in collaboration with CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and local communities.
- **Micro level:** Youth and students engaged through EPIC-WE CGJs.

At each level, the **impact analysis** tries to understand the specific challenges, opportunities, and knowledge gaps.

- **Macro (EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem):** Focused on understanding systemic issues such as cultural heritage policy development, cross-sector collaboration, and transformation.
- **Meso (Cultural Hub Model):** Assessed the needs of local and regional institutions for co-creative capacity-building and innovation in engaging with youth and cultural-creative tools.
- **Micro (CGJs):** Focused on the youth's cultural learning, skills development, and how game-making activities could foster engagement, empowerment, creativity and social cohesion in the context of cultural heritage.

The results of this analysis have been mapped out in expected short-term and long-term impacts of the project by using the [Change Pathway model](#) (figure 6) in the *Europeana Impact Playbook*.

Figure 11: [Change Pathway](#) (Europeana Playbook)

The Change Pathway is a tool to ideate, document and present the relationship between the things that you do and the impact that you have. It helps you to understand the relationship between the investments you are making (resources) and the impact you contribute to. By filling in this model, the activities of EPIC-WE could align desired outcomes in short and long term, as well as the desired impact of the project.

To structure the multi-layered CGJ activities into a structured and evidence-based impact model, the Change Pathway from the Europeana Impact Playbook was completed for each stakeholder group in the Quadruple Helix: Youth Citizens (YC), Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and Creative Industries (CIs).

The construction of the Change Pathway followed the Playbook’s recommended sequence:

1. **Internal domain - Resources, Activities and Outputs:** These were derived directly from D4.1 (Game-Making Framework), D4.2 (QH Operationalisation) and the CGJ implementation reports, ensuring consistency with the project’s documented interventions.

2. **External domain – Short-term Outcomes, Long-term Outcomes and Impact:**

These were aligned with the Specific Outcomes 1–4 in the Grant Agreement, ensuring that the Change Pathway reflects the expected immediate results, medium-term changes and long-term societal, cultural and economic impacts associated with EPIC-WE.

3. **Evidence mapping:** Each output and short-term outcome was connected to indicators that have been established in T6.1 and supported with observational data, testimonials and survey material from D2.3 and D4.2.

4. **Iterative refinement:** Following the DBR principles, the Change Pathway emerged iteratively through cross-hub comparison. Insights from the Aarhus, Hilversum and Óbidos CGJs were synthesised to identify patterns across contexts, while allowing for variation in local cultural themes, partnerships and youth groups.

Through this approach, the Change Pathway does not merely describe a theoretical sequence of impact, it constructs the lived process of cultural innovation observed across the 12 CGJs, translating it into a clear and transferable model that can be replicated by CHIs, CIs, and HEIs across Europe.

Phase 2: Impact Measurement

The Needs Analysis is designed to assess and address the specific needs of all key stakeholders – CHIs, HEIs, CIs and YCs – to ensure that they are aligned in terms of their goals and collaborative efforts within the cultural and creative innovation ecosystem. Phase 2 assessed the impact of CGJs through the key indicators defined under WP6, which serve as conceptual benchmarks rather than analytical codes. The empirical analyses underlying this assessment were conducted in other work packages – notably D4.1, which explored learning and design outcomes from the CGJs; D4.2, which analysed how the Quadruple Helix collaboration operationalised within the lifespan of the EPIC-WE project; D3.2, which discusses protocols for glocal DBR Cultural Game Jams; D3.3, which presents design and construction of the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, Cultural Hubs, and Cultural Game Jams, along with models, methods, and tools; and D2.3 which describes the results of the 12 Cultural Game Jam interventions to identify good practices that demonstrate the value of Cultural Game JamFs and game-making in helix ecosystems. D6.4 therefore synthesises those cross-hub results to present a holistic view of the project’s impact.

Focus on Qualitative Measurements: Developing Key Indicators

Given the complexity of the European values and the participatory nature of the project, the impact measurement primarily relies on qualitative indicators. These indicators qualified as a benchmark for measuring the collected data. The process of developing these indicators began with input gathered from consortium partners during EPIC-WE’s yearly consortium meeting in Óbidos, Portugal in February 2024. Two distinct exercises provided the foundational data for developing these indicators: the speed networking exercise and a Mentimeter survey:

1. Speed Networking Exercise

During this exercise, consortium members, consisting of CHI, CI and HEI members of the QH, interviewed each other and responded to a series of reflective questions. These questions focused on personal and professional contributions to the project, as well as the aspirations and excitement each participant felt towards EPIC-WE. The three primary questions were as follows:

1. What is the “EPICness” I can bring to the project and how can the project make the most out of me?
2. What am I most in love with or passionate about EPIC-WE – what excites me professionally?
3. What would I love to see as a result of EPIC-WE?

2. Mentimeter Survey

The Mentimeter survey posed a series of thought-provoking questions aimed at refining the internal and external values of the EPIC-WE project. These questions included:

1. The internal values of the consortium should be...
2. What are the most important values (of the EPIC-WE project)?
3. Our EPIC-WE Vision should be to...

4. The values radiating from our project & products should be... Looking at the project from the outside...
5. Ranking the EPIC-WE Core Concepts (from 1 to 5)
6. How important are the objectives and outcomes to achieve the values, visions and 'good project'?
7. Prioritise the 4 domains: 1) Clear instructions, management & structure, 2) Strong stories, strategy & impact, 3) Good science, research & knowledge, 4) Deep relations, alliances & outreach
8. Formulate as a quote: In your words – and to the world – what is the most epic about EPIC-WE?

These survey responses contributed to a deeper understanding of the values, objectives, and expectations surrounding the project, shaping the vision and direction for EPIC-WE.

The answers gathered from both the Speed Networking and Mentimeter Survey were then analysed to identify common themes and key values expressed by the consortium members. These insights helped inform the design of the qualitative indicators used to assess the project's impact. The indicators reflect both the personal motivations and the collective vision of the consortium, ensuring that they align with the overarching goals of the EPIC-WE project.

By utilising this participatory process, we ensured that the selected indicators were not only relevant but also deeply rooted in the values and aspirations of the consortium, providing a strong foundation for future assessments and project evolution.

Phase 3: Impact Narration

The qualitative data gathered from the CGJs were systematically analysed within D4.1, D4.2, T4.3 and D2.3. Building on these analyses, this report interprets their findings through the T6.1 Impact Indicators, benchmarks that can be seen as *conceptual lenses* rather than data categories. This alignment ensures that the impact narrative reflects a coherent analytical continuum across WPs 2, 4 and 6, integrating youth experience, institutional reflection and cross-hub synthesis into a shared story of impact. That way, we can understand *how* the CGJs produced cultural and social impact across hubs and partners.

The seven impact indicators (Knowledge & Cultural Understanding, Skill Development, Creativity & Imagination, Playfulness & Fun, Collaboration & Co-creation, Empowered Participation, and Social Connections) align well with the 7 principles in deliverables D4.1 describing how change occurs through cultural game-making, as well as with the 6 principles in D4.2, describing the conditions that enable democratic, cross-sector cultural innovation. In this report, these principles are operationalised into the 7 indicators that capture the actual effects of the CGJs on the YCs, CHIs, CIs and HEIs as whole ecosystems. Each indicator, therefore, reflects the interplay between the CGJ mechanisms (as described in D4.1), the QH cultural innovation model (as described in D4.2), and the Europeana Impact Playbook's emphasis on the participatory cultural value.

The following questions were used to interpret the analyses of D4.1, D4.2 and D2.3:

1. Knowledge & Cultural Understanding

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- Did the participants gain new cultural knowledge, insights, and perspectives during the CGJs?
- How did cultural encounters with artworks, cultural heritage sites, local stories, museum visits, etc. influence their knowledge and cultural understanding?

2. Skill development

- What new skills did participants gain or strengthen after participating in the CGJs?
- What new skills emerged across stakeholder groups?
- How were these skills exchanged within the QH ecosystem?

3. Creativity and imagination

- How did the participants and other stakeholders push creative boundaries or develop innovative ideas?
- How did the CGJs spark imagination and reinterpretation?
- What novel outcomes emerged from co-creation?

4. Playfulness and fun

- How did playfulness influence motivation, engagement and empowered participation?
- How did playful methods support cultural interpretation or creativity?
- How did playfulness affect group energy, atmosphere, and learning?

5. Collaboration and co-creation

- How did collaboration unfold across and within teams?
- How do the participants feel as a part of their team/group?
- How do they approach their tasks and what roles do they take on?
- How did different QH partners negotiate ideas, roles and decisions?
- What cross-sector relationships, partnerships or exchanges emerged?

6. Empowered Participation

- In what ways did participants experience agency, influence or ownership?
- How did the QH ecosystem enable shared responsibility among YCs, CHIs, CIs and HEIs?
- How did empowered participation show up in decision-making, facilitation or cultural interpretation?

7. Social Connections

- What new social connections, relationships or networks were formed?
- How did participants and the other stakeholders experience belonging, trust and group identity?
- How did these connections extend beyond the CGJs?

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This phase also incorporates testimonials from stakeholders at the macro, meso, and micro levels to refine and improve future impact assessment strategies. Furthermore, a Miro board was set up to visualise the impact narrative and further summarise, analyse, and brainstorm, allowing for a clearer interpretation of the analyses, as can be seen in Figure 8. This process helped identify key patterns that emerged during the CGJ

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To turn these insights into a compelling and engaging narrative, which can be found above, the Europeana Playbook [worksheet on Creating a Narrative Arc](#) was used, as shown in Figure 9. This tool provided a step-by-step guide for shaping the data into a meaningful narrative, making it easier to share, discuss, and learn from the data gathered.

Figure 13: Drafting the Impact Narrative using Europeana’s Narrative Arc Worksheet

With the narrative arc mapped out and the key themes identified, the next step was to transform these insights into a compelling narrative that helps to contextualise the findings, making them more engaging, memorable and actionable. This narrative can be found in chapter 2 of this report.

Use of Testimonials

The impact assessment presented in this deliverable draws on more than thirty testimonials collected throughout the EPIC-WE project. These testimonials come from multiple sources, including youth participants, Youth Advisory Board members, facilitators, cultural heritage professionals, creative industry mentors, academic partners, and contributions gathered through WP5 storytelling activities and expert interviews. Across these sources, testimonials capture participants' lived experiences, reflections, motivations and perceptions of change, offering a rich qualitative layer that complements the structured impact indicators.

In D6.4, testimonials are not treated as standalone evidence, but as interpretive material used to contextualise and deepen the indicator-based evaluation. They highlight how change was felt, articulated and observed across the hubs, providing insight into the human and relational dimensions of the Cultural Game Jams that are not fully captured through indicators alone. Testimonials are, therefore, used to illustrate patterns, validate emerging findings, and ground the assessment in authentic voices. When combined with the cross-hub analysis and the indicator framework, they help build a nuanced and meaningful understanding of the impact generated across the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem.

Phase 4: Evaluation

The evaluation phase examines the methods and tools used in the impact assessment. This phase involves reviewing:

- The overall effectiveness of the **change pathway** in achieving EPIC-WE's objectives.
- The adequacy of the **indicators** used to measure impact.

The aim of the evaluation is to assess the strength of these three methods above applied and to ensure that the impact assessment accurately reflects the outcomes of the EPIC-WE activities.

Conclusion

A Living, Evolving
Impact Narrative

05

5. Conclusion: A Living, Evolving Impact Narrative

The Cultural Game Jams implemented across the Aarhus, Hilversum and Óbidos Cultural Hubs demonstrated how game-making can act as a powerful catalyst for cultural participation, creativity and youth empowerment. By bringing together Youth Citizens, Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries and Higher Education Institutes through the developed Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub model, the CGJs transformed cultural heritage from passive consumption into a material for active, collaborative creation and empowered participation.

Across all twelve CGJ interventions, participants developed new cultural understanding, formed social connections, strengthened cultural, creative, technical and/or collaborative skills, and experienced a heightened sense of cultural agency and ownership. Over the course of the project, each hub learned how to refine the CGJs, using the CGJ Kit and adapting their structures, fostering deeper engagement, and ensuring that young participants had a real voice in the process. Cultural heritage became a dynamic resource for storytelling, imagination, and reinterpretation. Institutions, in turn, adopted new youth-centred practices, learned to “meet in the middle”, and experimented with co-creative approaches that strengthened cultural democracy.

The impact of the CGJs can be summarised as follows:

- Youth gained new knowledge of heritage and European values through hands-on cultural exploration and experimentation.
- Skills grew visibly, from creative ideation to communication, prototyping and teamwork.
- Creativity and imagination flourished, enabling reimagined cultural worlds and narratives.
- Playfulness fostered motivation, lowering barriers to learning and participation of youth citizens.
- Collaboration deepened, producing shared cultural agency across various stakeholders and sectors.
- Empowered participation emerged, with youth exercising voice, influence and ownership.
- Social connections were formed during the CGJs, supporting trust, belonging and continuing engagement across all relevant stakeholders.

Together, these outcomes show that CGJs are not only events, but engines of cultural innovation: participatory spaces where culture is experienced, remixed and created

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collaboratively amongst YCs, HEIs, CHIs and CIs. Moreover, the findings in this deliverable directly inform the validated QH Cultural Hub model, CGJ Kit and the emerging governance templates for Youth Advisory Boards, forming the evidence base for scalable replication across hubs.

Overall, these findings translate into actionable guidance for CHIs, CIs, HEIs and youth partners, such as integrating youth advisory structures early, building facilitation capacity for co-creation, and adopting iterative design approaches to sustain engagement. As EPIC-WE moves towards developing its public impact measurement guide (D6.5), the lessons from the QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs provide a replicable foundation for CHIs, CIs, and HEIs across Europe seeking to engage youth in meaningful, future-oriented cultural participation and co-creation.

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